

**THE MODERN WOMAN- BOLD AND BEAUTIFUL -
MODERN WOMAN IN NEW AGE LITERATURE AS
DEPICTED IN PAULO COELHO'S NOVELS: ELEVEN
MINUTES, BRIDA AND ADULTERY**

Rajani Ramachandran* & R. Vennila Nancy Christina**

* Assistant Professor, Department of English, Bharathamatha College of Arts and Science, Kozhinjampara, Palakkad, Kerala

** Assistant Professor, PG Department of English, Sree Saraswathi Thyagaraja College, Palani, Road, Pollachi, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: Rajani Ramachandran & R. Vennila Nancy Christina, "The Modern Woman- Bold and Beautiful - Modern Woman in New Age Literature as Depicted in Paulo Coelho's Novels: Eleven Minutes, Brida and Adultery", International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education, Volume 4, Issue 2, Page Number 39-41, 2018.

Copy Right: © IJMRME, 2018 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

Writers from ages have been trying to portray the life of women by presenting them as a traditional typecast who never questions and always settles down enduring all her sufferings. Paulo Coelho is one among the modern writer who has presented his woman protagonist in different shades of boldness and strength. Paulo Coelho's novel's brings out the normal woman who rises above the society and family that dominates her and sets rules for her. The bestselling novels of Paulo Coelho speak about how a woman can challenge her society and grow up to fulfill her dreams and happiness. The main Protagonist spoken about in this article is beautiful but very bold woman who are not the traditional type. They are neither bound to religious or societal domination. They take every risk, commit sins without regrets and allow herself to immerse in the world of liberation. Paulo Coelho's depiction of Maria from *Eleven Minutes*, Pilar from *By the River Piedra I sat weeping* and Linda from *Adultery* are discussed in this article. His feminine sides are best revealed through this novels. Self realization and happiness is achieved by these women inspite of all hurdles in life to establish their own identity.

Key Words: Bold, Beautiful, Traditional, Struggle, Self –Actualisation & Identity Etc

Introduction:

Pilgrimage to the soul is an important phase that is essential for life which gives a human being the purpose for a meaningful existence. It helps one capable of answering many of the riddles that life has inflicted. It has been a challenging question for great souls to ask "who am I?" The world has witnessed many great personalities and saints spending a great part of their life searching and meditating to find out the essence of their existence and the enjoy the ecstasy of attaining self-actualization. This journey helped them to know closely a broad world of truths in depth.

Woman, the most beautiful and enchanting creature ever created by God is the greater truth that no sage or saint has been able to find. A ocean which no one has been able to swim across without turbulence. The essence of woman is always a puzzle to her male counterpart and keeps slipping into an Illusion. Modern writers have contributed a great deal of this power and strength of woman through their writings. Unlike the 19th century writers who created woman as a soul who could dominate by the male protagonist. She did not have a space for herself. She was a mere object of enjoyment and reproduction. Everyone forgot that she had her own soul, emotions and strength and nobody even tried to explore it until few writers like Henrik Ibsen, Jane Austen broke the conventional lover girl typecast and presented "The Doll's House" and "Emma", with a different angle of the modern woman.

Later in 20th century, many great writers formed their own groups to raise voice against the second ary position of women in the society. They struggled against their low status and discrimination and they these writers came to be known as Feminist. Feminism became a cultural movement and tried to secure women with equality in all ways of life. Now in this modern era, we have immensely talented writers who have played a major role in showcassing the soul searching woman who stakes all her emotions and makes her empowered, no matter what she loses emotionally but finally gets her contentment and self realization. The portrayal of determined woman with all her weakness and strength can be widely enjoyed in the novels of the great Brazilian writer Paulo Coelho, one of the bestseller writers of this century.

Review of Literature:

This article tries to go through a short journey of the soulful woman Protagonist from Paulo Coelho's novels '*Eleven Minutes*, "*By the River Piedra I sat down and wept*" and "*Adultery*". We can realize how the feminine element has occupied a fundamental space in his own life. Compassion was the new element he found out from the struggle he faced with his masculine identity. "All my life has been governed by feminine energy,

by women”- this vision of Paulo Coelho talks more about this writer. The New Age Literature has welcomed this writer for his beautiful portrayal of woman. He doesn't not present his female protagonist traditionally. They are neither cruel, wicked nor resentful in nature. They are neither stuff of ridicule. Generally the woman in classical age is portrayed as a temptress, jealousy overriding emotional and greedy. But with time, the New Age writer like Paulo Coelho has been successful in bringing grandeur in his entire female protagonist.

The Bold and the Beautiful:

MARIA:

Eleven Minutes depicts the story of a young Brazilian Village girl who leaves her hometown to Geneva and Switzerland. Her desire to seek adventure and happiness leads her to pursue her a career in prostitution. Maria experiences pain, pleasure and love and finally decides to correct her path.

Maria is different from other girls in her town. She is beautiful but also bold enough to have a desire for herself. She loves adventure where her friends are woven into a traditional culture of getting married and raise a family. She realizes that money is essential for her dreams to come true. Thus she is tricked into working in a night club as a samba dancer at Rio de Janeiro. Maria realizes that she is forced now into a lifestyle much more restricted than the one she had imagined. Maria has to struggle to live away her life through hardships and signing up a modeling assignment at a fashion show. But the struggle never ends and she has to sleep with many for her survival. Thus begins Maria's career as a prostitute, and which she does because of its good money. During her turbulent life in Geneva, She experiences various types of sex but restricts her soul from entering into the process.

Maria finally falls in love with a painter not knowing whether she will marry him but at least happy to have found mutual love. This is something that's going to elude her life...she thought. For the first time, Maria loves with her soul as well as with her body.

“Everything tells me that I am about to make a wrong decision, but making mistakes is just part of life. What does the world want of me? Does it want me to take no risks, to go back to where I came from because I didn't have the courage to say “yes” to life”.

PILAR:

Pilar is the central character who goes onto a pilgrimage to find her inner self in the Novel *By the River Piedra I Sat Down and Wept*. Earlier in this story, She is reunited with her childhood friend who has spent ten years traveling around the world. He attempts to teach Pilar, a studious catholic to open her her mind to various possibilities. Pilar being a reserved and cautious girl, taught by the society not to question the authority has many struggles in her life. She feels that she is dissatisfied and has to suppress her happiness for the rules that society has set.

Pilar takes a journey to France, she sets herself loose but turns around the fear that is deep inside her that avoids her to take a leap. Finally she lets her soul open to find something new and transforms into a person who can truly love and live a life the way she hopes. She explores the concept of love and the virtue of the masculine and feminine sides of God. Pilar finally forms a passionate love and connection that transcends physical contact and grows more in depth and spiritual. She discovers who truly she is and what she wants out of her life. This enables her to take action and achieve it.

“No one can avoid defeat. That is why it is better to lose a few battles in the fight for your dreams than to be defeated without even knowing why you are fighting”

Linda

Linda, the protagonist from *Adultery is* in her 30s who has a rich husband and two lovable kids. She is a modern woman balancing her career as a journalist and a doting family. Yet she feels trapped in routine and mired life devoid of passion and struggles with boredom, depression and envy. The spark of her life is set aflame when she she meets her old boyfriend Jacob who is a politician now and married to a philosophy professor. Linda gradually starts an affair with him and they end up having sex. Linda is not sure why she is attracted to Jacob and keeps questioning her own thoughts, troubles and motives. From this point on, they both secretly meet and continue their affair. Owing to the affair, Linda feels satisfied with life and a new sense of freedom, but her illusions carry on. She decides to get psychological help. During this time, she interviews Cuban Sham.

Adultery makes sense to Linda and her relationship with Jacob helps her overcome her depression and displeasure with life. The adultery, in some ways, strengthens her relationship with her husband and things begin to get back to normal. Linda's sufferings throughout the journey of self-discovery, after meeting Jacob, take a toll on her emotional balance. Finally, when Linda visits three psychiatrists for the problem of Having “murderous thoughts,” she is diagnosed to have emotional problems that comprise “Transference,” “hormonal disturbances,” and over usage of drugs. The oxymoron of animalism of Jacob who doesn't seem to have any meaningful connection with anyone and the saintliness of Linda's husband who doesn't fit in the stereotype of an affluent man, are the extremes and Linda seems to be torn apart between the two. In addition to Linda's self-discovery and search for meaningfulness in life, At the end, when she revisits Switzerland with her husband and recalls their fun-filled Honeymoon trip to the same place, she has a revelation while paragliding. She mentions

that the “world is perfect,” and to “love abundantly is to live abundantly.” She feels it is love for Oneself and others that makes our existence meaningful. She carves out a niche for herself to attain completeness and opines, “All you can do is look at Love, fall in love with Love, and imitate it.” All her trials and tribulations seem to vanish as clarity enters her mind. Happy and Contented, she declares, “We will go outside to celebrate” “The walls have all fallen, I have just been reborn”

Conclusion:

This article presents how Paulo Coelho has presented his female protagonist representing the modern woman. The new woman signifies the rising of woman into a new realization that she has a inner soul whom she has to satisfy. She finds the society and her own family setting rules and boundaries which stop her from even weaving a life for her. The patriarchal dominance is overcome by this woman. Paulo Coelho has created his woman protagonist on the lines of new Age Literature. They display more boldness and don't represent the typecast traditional women who are jealous, greedy or just passive survivors. They are indeed fighters who surpass their struggles and achieve their freedom. Coelho represents contemporary woman as bold and beautiful in its entire realistic manner. They are memorable, mystic and extraordinarily bold who are true paradigms of modern liberal feminism. The traditional concept about the purity of women is challenged through his leading ladies.

References:

1. Coelho, Paulo. 2014. *Adultery*. New York: Alfred A. Knopf.
2. Eagleton, Terry. 1983. *Literary Theory: An Introduction*. Oxford: Blackwell Publishers.
3. Ellis, Albert, et al. 2009. *Psychoanalysis in theory and practice*. In *Personality theories: Critical perspectives*.
4. Coelho, Paulo. *Adultery*. Gurgaon: Random House India, 2014.
5. Franklin, Benjamin. “Where there's Marriage without Love, there will be Love without Marriage.” *Poor Richard's Almanacs*
6. www.theguardian.com
7. www.wikipedia
8. www.enotes.com